

STAGES OF COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY TEACHERS

Ibadullaev G'ayrat Akmuradovich

Independent researcher of Urgench State Pedagogical Institute
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Introduction.

The main goal of teaching physics is the ability to think logically about the role of physics education in the development of science and technology, production areas and life, mental development, the formation of the potential for self-awareness, national, universal human to acquire the knowledge necessary for the formation of values and to continue their social life and education, to teach them how to use them in their daily lives, and to form the potential to apply physical knowledge to life by connecting practical activities with broadening the worldview of students regarding the physical landscape of the world and development.

In the process of teaching, it is important to teach students to apply the important rules of science in order to understand and explain the nature of physical phenomena, conclusions from the results of experiments, and the operation of tools and devices. Highlighting the main material in each section of the physics course helps the teacher to focus students' attention on the issues they need to master deeply and rigorously. Physical experiments are an integral part of teaching physics at all stages of education, a source of knowledge and a teaching method.

Development of educational competence in future physics teachers through experiments requires a number of typical professional skills from the teacher-in-training based on standard projects. The composition of methodological actions in teaching the methodology and technique of the experiment is sufficiently complex, and it is necessary to observe several rules in its implementation.

The technology of developing students' educational competence through experimenting and demonstration is most effective when organized on the basis of a step-by-step approach. These stages can be divided into intellectual, practical-operational, technological and reflexive stages.

Intellectual stage: It is known that the formation and analysis of the goal as a sample of the final product during the experiment is a component of professional and methodical activity. At the theoretical stage, it is necessary to carefully analyze the material in order to consciously set the purpose of the experiment. Also, he should be familiar with the physical theory and laws related

to the subject of the experiment. The student must answer a series of questions during a short conversation with the teacher (these questions may be given in the recommended literature or methodological instructions) or get permission to perform the experiment as a result of the tests.

Practical-operational stage: The student, who has received permission to perform the experiment, begins to assemble the device. After the device is assembled, the teacher checks it. After making sure that the device is assembled correctly, the teacher gives instructions on performing the experiment, drawing the student's attention to the main parameters of the methodology and technique of performing the experiment. setting an example will have a positive effect. Further experiments are carried out independently by the student. The student performs calculations after repeating the experiment several times and recording the results. It calculates the average arithmetic value of the experimentally obtained values of the measured quantity. Then it calculates the experimental errors.

During the experiment, the students who performed the above actions develop such competencies as choosing equipment for the experiment, assembling the device, placing the equipment in a logical sequence, performing measurements, understanding the physical nature of the observed phenomenon or process, and drawing conclusions.

The process of developing academic competence requires students to repeat the above methodical actions many times during independent work in class and outside of class. As a result, the activity technique turns into a skill, and then, due to frequent repetition, into a skill and competence.

The basis for choosing a physical experiment is:

- *educational tasks of this educational stage;*
- *the structure of physical learning and research activities of students;*
- *the main stages of forming physical concepts;*
- *experience of creative activity.*

When choosing an experiment, educational tasks should be considered as the leader, because they ultimately determine the structure and logic of studying the educational material, the organizational forms of student activity, and the methods of presenting the material. Students' cognitive activity rises from the reproductive level to the creative reproductive level. The integration of professional knowledge and technological actions plays an important role in the implementation of tasks. Pedagogical management in the method of task-based education is based on interiorization and exteriorization.

The cyclical process of interaction of internal and external actions helps students to master teaching methods and tools more fully. Repeating the solution of operational tasks many times allows you to strengthen the algorithms of pedagogical activity in memory, to understand and understand the leading structure of actions, and later to use them in professional activities, you will acquire the competence of repetition. The process of forming the skills of explaining physical phenomena and entering physical quantities is relatively complex, and it requires not only knowledge of the methods of teaching activities, but also a deep understanding of their essence.

Technological stage: At this stage, students solve methodological problems, develop a technological map to study concepts, phenomena, laws, etc., design a part of the lesson with the help of demonstration experiments and frontal experiments. A necessary element of solving the problem is to explain the physical nature of the observed processes. The reproductive and creative-reproductive level of methodological tasks involves solving them in accordance with the theoretical standard and taking into account the specific conditions of the teaching situation. The main focus is on achieving practical learning goals.

Reflexive stage: This stage is final and summative, in which it is possible to defend the performed physical experiment and perform introspection (in-depth study and knowledge of the experiment, individual thinking) according to the following algorithm:

- 1) show a part of the experiment as a film with a demonstration experience;
 - 2) justify why the experimental fragment was chosen;
 - 3) to give examples of the fields of application of physical experiments.
- 4) Reveal the method of conducting this experiment as a teacher. The work on the purposeful selection of the experiment significantly optimizes the experimental preparation of future physics teachers, develops initiative, creativity in preparing demonstration experiments, the use of hand-made tools, and the competence of conducting experiments at home.

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